

A CRITICAL PERSPECTIVE ON THE TECHNOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE INFORMATION SOCIETY

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Abstract

Technology and society have always interacted with one another throughout the history. This interaction between the two has led to some significant changes in the world. Each new technological advancement has catalyzed a corresponding revolution, from the Agricultural and Industrial Revolutions to the contemporary Informatics Revolution. The latter, propelled by advancements in information and communication technologies (ICT), has ushered in what we now recognize as the information society. This research delves into the pivotal role of ICT in shaping this societal landscape. Drawing upon a comprehensive literature review and theoretical frameworks of post-industrial society, this study scrutinizes the mechanisms driving the emergence of the information society. The findings underscore the intricate interplay between technology and societal dynamics in this evolutionary process. While ICT undoubtedly plays a central role, the construction of the information society emerges as a multifaceted phenomenon, transcending mere technological determinism. Thus, this research validates the hypothesis positing that the information society arises from the nuanced interaction between societal forces and information technologies.

Keywords: Post-Industrial Society, Information Society, The information Age, Information Technologies Revolution, Information and Communication Technologies.

INTRODUCTION

The developments in the field of technology are also causing changes in the social structures they interact with. It is a reality subject to a complex network of relationships as to whether technology or society will be the driving force of change in this interaction process. Therefore, considering the mutual interaction between technology and society as the source of change seems to be a relatively rational approach. Indeed, society can play a significant role in the production of technology, while technology can also take the lead in bringing about innovations in society. Based on the aforementioned approach, it can be assumed that the effective interaction process between society and information and communication technologies plays a crucial role in the development of the information society.

The information society is characterized as a new type of society that represents the ultimate stage of societal development, where knowledge becomes the dominant value in every aspect of society. It is a multidimensional social phenomenon that describes the changes brought about by the use of knowledge in all dimensions of society, including technological, economic, socio-cultural, and political aspects. The primary factor mediating the dominance of knowledge in the development of this societal phenomenon is technology, particularly information and communication technologies. In other words, just as in industrial societies where machines and capital occupy a central place, in the information society, information and data blocks are filled with information technologies. Thus, in the industrial society, capital is what matters, whereas in the information society, knowledge is paramount; the only difference is that power and authority are gained

through the accumulation of capital in industrial societies, while in the information society, power is attained through the sharing of knowledge.

Due to the multidimensionality mentioned above, the information society cannot be considered solely as a reality generated by information technologies. For information societies, knowledge is the goal, while information and communication technologies merely serve as tools. However, the existence of advanced technology is undeniable in order to produce, store, use, and share the knowledge that creates such a significant change and acquires a new form in society. Therefore, in a world where knowledge is a source of power and authority, the importance of advanced information and communication technologies cannot be denied. To be influential in the field of knowledge management, it is necessary to obtain the power to produce, develop, use, and disseminate this advanced technology called information technology. In other words, the path to becoming an information society lies in having information technology and using these tools effectively and efficiently. Therefore, in this study, the question of whether information and communication technologies are independent variables in the development of the information society has been identified as the research question. To answer the research question, the aim is to examine the role of information and communication technologies in the creation of information societies. Since the research is exploratory, it is assumed that the effective interaction process between information and communication technologies and the development of the information society is the fundamental assumption. The theories of the information society available in the existing literature have been mainly used as data for testing the assumption of this theoretical study.

FROM INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES TO THE INFORMATION SOCIETY: A CONCEPTUAL ANALYSIS

It would not be inaccurate to say that the two most prominent concepts today are "the information society" and "information and communication technologies." Indeed, computer and internet technology have become an integral part of human life in the age we live in. This new form of society, in which information is extensively used in socio-economic life through these technologies, is referred to as the information society. Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) - or recently referred to as "Info Communication" - are used to denote "all technologies that enable the collection, processing, storage, and transmission of information from one place to another through communication and computer technologies." In other words, "information technologies encompass all technologies including microelectronics and data transmission, as well as fax machines, mobile phones, cable television, computers, information networks, videotex, software, and online databases" (<http://www.msxlabs.org>).

The concept of the Information Society is used interchangeably with terms such as "Information Society," "Digital Society", "Post-Industrial Society," "Post-Capitalist Society," "Post-Industrial Society," and "Cybernetic Society". The Information Society is defined as "a comprehensive term describing societies in which activities related to the production, processing, and distribution of information are considered as fundamental inputs and sources of power in economic, political, social, and cultural domains" (<http://www.btk.gov.tr>), although there is no globally accepted single definition. Another definition describes the Information Society as a form of society shaped by technology and information, driven by the dynamics of globalization and development – post-industrial. While the term Information Society is the most commonly used, Castells makes an analytical distinction between "information society" and "informational society." According to Castells, the term Information Society is important in all societies, including medieval Europe, as it emphasizes the role of information in society. In contrast, the term "informational" or "informative" is based on a specific form of social organization where the production, processing, and transmission of information become the main sources of production and power due to new technological conditions in the current historical period (Castells, 1997: 21). While acknowledging Castells' accurate observation, this study opts for the widely used term "Information Society" for consistency.

Although the Information Society may appear as a relatively new concept, it is rumored that its foundations were laid before the 1900s. However, it is noted that the term "age of communication" was first used by Canadian communication theorist Marshall McLuhan in 1962, while American economist Fritz Machlup also used the term "information society" (Geray, 1997: 37). According to another view, the term Information Society was first introduced by Japanese scholar Yoneji Masuda in his work "The Information Society: As Post-

Industrial Society" (1981) (Sarigöz, 2012: 73). Additionally, there are different opinions regarding the first users of the term "information society," with Porat (1978) and Masuda (1990) being among them (Yılmaz, 1998: 149).

The mind-boggling advancements in information technologies during the transition to the knowledge society have transformed the world into a small village by bringing people and societies closer together. With the affordability of information technology and the introduction of personal computers in the early 1980s, people now have the ability to access all kinds of information anytime and anywhere they desire. The internet technology, which enables millions of computers worldwide to connect to a network, largely facilitates access to information and databases. A person connected to the internet from anywhere in the world not only has access to information banks located elsewhere but also has the opportunity to transfer the acquired knowledge to their computer (Sheker, 2005: 377). Consequently, knowledge societies benefit from the technical advantages provided by information technologies, enabling the structural transformation or reconfiguration of society on one hand, while providing opportunities and resources for the production of knowledge through the scientific accumulation gained in the field of information and technology on the other. Information technologies, feeling compelled to innovate in order to meet the needs of this constantly evolving and advancing society that closely monitors new developments in the knowledge society, continue to progress in the technological field as part of the mutual interactive development process.

AN OVERVIEW OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES

Information Communication Technologies (ICT) are the product of technological advancements recorded in the era of information we currently live in. Although they first emerged in our era, it is noted that the foundations of these technological advancements were laid in earlier periods. For instance, according to Calik and Cinar, today's technology has emerged as a product of accumulated knowledge dating back to the earliest periods of history, such as the discovery of fire, the invention of the wheel, and the progress of civilizations. Therefore, contemporary ICT can be seen as a continuation of philosophical thought forms that have deep roots in ancient times. In short, the scientific and technological developments that created ICT are considered as a result of the scientific knowledge accumulated throughout the history of civilization.

When we talk about information technology, the first thing that comes to mind is computers, which are products of modern technology. With computers, thanks to information and communication technologies that can store, process, and generate new information as desired, humans can both create new products with their creativity and solve emerging problems through technology (Sarigöz, 2012: 74). Additionally, the indispensable position of the telephone in our daily lives has given way to new technological possibilities with the increasing need for communication and information

circulation, leading to the rise of mobile telecommunications and enhancing users' mobility; thus, various services in this field have come to the forefront (Aydin, 2007: 1). In other words, the invention of mobile phones has brought a new dimension to the communication industry. Particularly, the transformation of smartphones into handheld computers capable of performing many advanced functions beyond communication, such as accessing online databases and social networks for data transfer, has revolutionized the field of information technology. The advancements made in the transfer of all kinds of data and information, in addition to their production and processing, demonstrate that progress in information and communication technologies has reached incredible heights. Indeed, in the twenty-first century, known as the age of information, it is noted that mobile telecommunications devices and the internet, which have become increasingly indispensable parts of our daily lives, have constituted the fastest-growing segment of information and communication technologies in the last decade. The increase in knowledge accumulation and the growing need for information in economic activities lead to the development of telecommunications systems with different features and sometimes their combined usage (Aydin, 2007: 105). These boundless advancements in knowledge management suggest that information technologies are progressing towards becoming significant sources of power that could potentially change the balance of power in the world, both in terms of tools and hardware.

CONCLUSION

Our contemporary societies are rapidly evolving towards a different type of society, the "knowledge society," where knowledge increasingly replaces the production factors of the industrial society. In this new societal form, the extensive use of knowledge, which has been growing like a snowball throughout civilization history, has become intertwined with advanced technological tools. The mutual interaction between society and technology in this structure has created the notion that information technologies are the driving force behind the creation of the knowledge society. However, based on the examinations and evaluations above, this study concludes that the construction of the knowledge society is not merely explained by technological factors but is a complex social phenomenon. It is determined that the knowledge society is not just a techno-society; rather, it is a model of society with socio-economic, cultural, and psychological foundations, representing the society of the future. While the role of information technologies in the establishment of the knowledge society cannot be denied, it must be remembered that knowledge and communication technologies are products of knowledge and culture within society. There is still no definitive judgment on whether it is society or information technologies that initiated the change towards becoming a knowledge society. Therefore, it is confirmed that in this process, there is a mutual interaction between information technologies in creating the knowledge society and the knowledge society in developing information technologies.

The knowledge society is considered to be the culmination of a long historical process, which could be characterized as the ultimate stage in the history of civilization. Therefore, the knowledge society cannot be seen as an independent development solely occurring in the age of information, nor can it be evaluated merely as a form of social organization established by information and communication technologies. The establishment of the knowledge society corresponds to a complex and lengthy process of social development that cannot be explained solely by technological determinism based on developments in the information age. At least, the evolutionary approaches of some post-industrial or knowledge society theorists suggest this. The development of the knowledge society, even when explained through the adventure of knowledge, can be evaluated within the historical development trajectory of societies without deviating too far from an evolutionary line. In this historical trajectory, scientific and technological developments from the Industrial Age play a significant role. It is believed that the accumulation of knowledge and machine technology during this period had a significant contribution to the development of information technologies. The advent of machine technology in the Industrial Age deeply influenced the mode of production and production relations of the era. Mass production in established factories led to the generation of surplus value, which in turn led to an increase in capital. The increase in capital resulted in the ownership of the means of production by capitalists, leading to the separation of production forces and the imbalance in favor of capital against labor.

The inequality observed at the international level regarding ownership of information tools can also be encountered at the national level. Along with income and education disparities, inequalities in the ownership and access opportunities to information tools among the members of society can limit the transition opportunities to a knowledge society by creating inequality. Information tools, in terms of access and usage differences, can lead to injustices among different social classes, technically termed as "digital divide," thus giving rise to certain problems in creating a fair and balanced knowledge society. However, at least in the aspect mentioned, it is expected that the knowledge society will be democratic. If access opportunities to information and communication tools are not distributed equally among all individuals in a way that does not lead to any discrimination within society—which is never possible from a socio-economic perspective—then a comprehensive transition to a knowledge society cannot be discussed. In other words, if access opportunities to information tools, which are only shared by the higher socio-economic strata of society, are not considered sufficient for the overall construction of a knowledge society, the transition to a knowledge society may seem utopian for some societies from a socio-economic perspective. More precisely, the transition to a knowledge society is imagined to be quite smooth at the theoretical level, with everyone in society being harmoniously involved in the process like a pleasant dream journey. In reality, however, rather than har-

mony in social life, there are disparities, socio-economic problems, inequalities and conflicts among classes, certain socio-cultural values, indicating that the transition to a knowledge society is a multidimensional process that needs to be evaluated not only technologically but also socio-economically and politically. In short, the transition to a knowledge society is not simply a formation determined by information tools but rather should be considered as a formation generated by the mutual interaction process between information technologies and society.

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